

Physico-Chemical Studies of Emulsions: Part II. Breaking of Emulsions by Electrolytes

K. D. Jain and M. K. Sharma*

Effect of electrolytes on the stability and breaking of emulsions stabilized by single surfactants, binary mixtures of surfactants, binary mixtures of protein and surfactants and tertiary mixtures of protein and surfactants has been studied. The stabilising effect of emulsifying agents towards electrolytes has been found to increase in the order : (a) Manoxol IB(MIB), Manoxol OT(MOT), MIB + Tween 60(T. 60), MOT + T. 60, MIB + Triton $\times 100$ (T $\times 100$), MOT + T $\times 100$, MIB + Gelatin (GEL), MOT + GEL, MIB + T.60 + GEL, MOT + T.60 + GEL, MIB + T $\times 100$ + GEL, MOT + T $\times 100$ + GEL and (b) Cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB), Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB), CPB + T.60, CTMAB + T.60, CPB + T $\times 100$, CTMAB + T $\times 100$, CPB + GEL, CTMAB + GEL, CPB + T.60 + GEL, CTMAB + T.60 + GEL, CPB + T $\times 100$ + GEL, CTMAB + T $\times 100$ + GEL. The demulsification power of anions decreases as follows : phosphate, citrate, sulphate, thiosulphate, oxalate, carbonate, dichromate, acetate, chloride, nitrate and bromide : for cations : aluminium, iron (ic), magnesium, strontium, barium, cobalt, copper (ic), potassium, sodium and ammonium..

Demulsification or breaking of emulsions that is, conversion into two macroscopic liquid layers is carried out by chemical¹⁻⁴, physical^{5,6} and mechanical^{7,8} means.

In continuation of previous work⁹⁻¹¹, the present paper reports the effect of electrolytes on the stability and breaking of emulsions taking single surfactants (anionic and cationic), binary mixtures of surfactants (anionic + nonionic and cationic + nonionic), binary mixtures of protein and surfactants (gelatin + anionic and gelatin + cationic) and tertiary mixtures of protein and surfactants (gelatin + anionic + nonionic and gelatin + cationic + nonionic) as emulsifying agents and water and kerosene oil as continuous and disperse phases.

* Present Address : Instruments Research and Development Establishment, Dehra Dun, INDIA.

1. Aaron Miller, *J. Soc. Cosmet. Chem.*, 1967, **18**(3), 169.
2. S. Miyamoto, *Mem. Fac. Sci. Kyushu Univ. Ser. C.*, 1960, No. 3, 93.
3. M. Van den Tempel, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1953, **72**, 442.
4. S. F. Chmumin, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1962, **186**, 79.
5. D. N. Levchenko, A. S. Ermilov, G. A. Teplykh and N. K. Volobuev, *Prinenenie ul' traakukustii Issled Veschestva*, 1961, No. 14, 337.
6. M. Dzhuvarly and N. V. Klimova, *Uchenye Zapiski Azerbaidzhan Gosularst. Univ. im S. M. Kirova*, 1957, No. 2, 49.
7. R. Schiel, *Ger. P.* 802, 344, Feb. 8, 1951.
8. E. V. Truter, "Wool Wax", p. 117, New York, Interscience Publishers, Inc., 1956.
9. K. D. Jain and M. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1970, **47**, 989.
10. K. D. Jain and M. K. Sharma, *Res. & Ind.* (accepted).
11. M. K. Sharma and K. D. Jain, *J. Sci. Res.* (accepted).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Photographic gelatin (GEL) used, was prepared according to a method described by one of the authors earlier¹². Sodium dioctyl sulphosuccinate (MOT-anionic surfactant), sodium dibutyl sulphosuccinate (MIB-anionic surfactant), cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB-cationic surfactant), cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB-cationic surfactant) and alkyl aryl polyether alcohol (T×100—anionic surfactant) were B.D.H. England products and poly-oxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (T.60-nonionic surfactant) was obtained from M/S Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd., London. Citrate, thiosulphate, oxalate, chloride, nitrate and bromide of sodium, anhydrous sulphate, carbonate and acetate of sodium and chlorides of magnesium, strontium, barium, cobalt, potassium and ammonium were of B.D.H. AR grade and phosphate and dichromate of sodium, anhydrous aluminium chloride, hydrated ferric chloride and cupric chloride were B.D.H. LR products. In all the experiments double distilled kerosene oil (K.O., b.p. 205° and sp. gr. 7948925 at 30°) and double distilled water (pH 6.2 and conductivity $.85 \times 10^{-6}$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) were used.

Preparation of emulsions : Emulsions were prepared under following conditions by Agent-in-Water method¹³.

- (a) Fixed ratio of water and K.O. (2 : 1)
- (b) Fixed concentrations of emulsifying agents.
- (c) Equal concentrations of emulsifying agents.

To the aqueous solution of single or mixture of emulsifying agents, K.O. was added slowly with constant stirring. The emulsion thus made was homogenized by considerable agitation with the help of Braun Emulsifier.

Effect of electrolytes : An approximate value of the demulsification concentration of an electrolyte was obtained by running from a burette into a definite volume (10 ml.) of emulsion, solutions of known concentrations of electrolyte. Having obtained approximate values for the demulsification concentration, solutions of the electrolytes of appropriate concentrations were prepared and exact amount of electrolyte necessary for breaking of emulsion was determined as described below in the case of electrolyte potassium chloride and emulsion stabilized by MOT.

A .1M solution of potassium chloride (7.456 g. per litre) was prepared and from this a series of 5 ml. portions of diluted solutions were prepared by mixing in small test tubes .5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0 and 4.5 ml. of potassium chloride solution with 4.5, 4.0, 3.5, 3.0, 2.5, 2.0, 1.5, 1.0 and .5 ml. of double distilled water respectively. 5 ml. of the emulsion stabilised by MOT were placed in ten test tubes of the same size and to each of these was added 5 ml. of potassium chloride solution of the desired strength. After each addition the contents were mixed well by inverting the tube three or four times and then the tubes were placed in a rack for 6 hrs.

12. M. K. Sharma, *Invention Intelligence*, 1969, 4, 24.
13. P. Becher, "Emulsions : Theory and Practice". p. 267, New York, Reinhold Publishing Corp., 1966.
14. J. W. Mc Bain, "Colloid Science", p. 177, Boston, D. C. Heath and Co., 1950.

In the above case, .5 ml. of the original potassium chloride solution contained 0.00005 mole (or 0.05 millimole) and since this amount was then finally diluted to 10 ml., the concentration of the potassium chloride in the mixed solution would be 5 millimoles per litre and in the other cases the concentrations would be 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45 millimoles per litre. At the end of six hours, it was ascertained that in which case breaking of emulsion into two phases had occurred. It was found that in the last seven solutions, demulsification had taken place but not in the first two, where the emulsions were quite stable. Thus the demulsification value of potassium chloride lay between 10 and 15 millimoles per litre. Further experiments with concentrations of 10 and 15 millimoles per litre were carried out in order to fix the value more closely.

The above experiments were performed with each electrolyte and emulsion and the amount of different electrolytes required for breaking the emulsion into water and K.O layers was determined.

The results are summarised in Tables I-VIII

DISCUSSION

It may be seen from Tables I to IV that the minimum concentration in millimoles per litre of various electrolytes required to cause demulsification of emulsions stabilized by anionic surfactants and their mixtures increases, with respect to emulsifying agents, as follows :—

- (a) MOT, MOT+T. 60, MOT+T×100, MOT+GEL. MOT+T.60+GEL, MOT+T×100+GEL.
- (b) MIB, MIB+T. 60. MIB+T×100. MIB+GEL. MIB+T. 60+GEL, MIB+T×100+GEL.

For emulsions stabilized by both types of anionic surfactants and their mixtures, the stabilizing power of emulsifying agents towards electrolytes may be arranged in the following manner :—

$$\text{MOT+T}\times 100+\text{GEL} > \text{MIB+T}\times 100+\text{GEL} > \text{MOT+T.60+GEL} > \text{MIB+T.60+GEL} > \text{MOT+GEL} > \text{MIB+GEL} > \text{MOT+T}\times 100 > \text{MIB+T}\times 100 > \text{MOT+T.60} > \text{MIB+T.60} > \text{MOT} > \text{MIB}$$

In the case of emulsions stabilized by cationic surfactants and their mixtures (Tables V to VIII), the demulsification value of electrolytes with respect to emulsifying agents increases in the order :—

- (a) CPB, CPB+T.60, CPB+T×100. CPB+GEL, CPB+T.60+GEL, CPB+T×100+GEL.
- (b) CTMAB, CTMAB+T.60, CTMAB+T×100, CTMAB+GEL, CTMAB+T.60+GEL, CTMAB+T×100+GEL.

TABLE I
Emulsions stabilized by MOT and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emulsion Type : O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O. = 10 ml. ; MOT = .05 g. ; T.60 = .05 g. ; T × 100 = .05 g. ; GEL = .05 g.

Emul- sion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Sod. Phosphate	Sod. Citrate	Sod. Sulphate	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre					Sod. Nitrate	Sod. Bromide
					Thio- sulphate	Oxalate Carbonate	Dichro- mate	Acetate	Sod. Chloride		
1.	MOT	1.15	1.20	4.05	4.20	4.55	4.70	4.90	12.5	14.5	15
2.	MOT+T.60	1.60	1.72	6.25	6.50	6.75	7.20	7.55	19.0	22.0	23
3.	MOT+T × 100	3.42	3.68	12.40	13.25	14.20	14.90	15.40	37.5	45.0	46.5
4.	MOT+GEL	26	29	112	114	116	117	119	228	238	242
5.	MOT+T.60+GEL	31	34	122	124	127	129	131	248	260	263
6.	MOT+T × 100+GEL	33	37	133	134	135	138	140	273	282	286

TABLE II
Emulsions stabilized by MOT and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emulsion Type :—O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O. = 10 ml. ; MOT = .05 g. ; T.60 = .05 g. ; T × 100 = .05 g. ; GEL = .05 g.

Emul- sion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Alumi- num Chloride	Ferric Chloride	Magne- sium Chloride	Stron- tium Chloride	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre.					Ammo- nium Chloride
						Barium Chloride	Cobalt Chloride	Cupric Chloride	Potassium Chloride	Sodium Chloride	
1.	MOT	.0890	.0985	.50	.54	.57	.60	.64	13.0	14.0	16.0
2.	MOT+T.60	.125	.147	.80	.83	.87	.91	.96	20	20.5	24.5
3.	MOT+T × 100	.252	.290	1.50	1.60	1.72	1.84	1.95	40	43.0	49
4.	MOT+GEL	1.35	1.45	7.0	7.60	8.00	8.5	9.0	231	235	246
5.	MOT+T.60+GEL	1.54	1.68	10.0	10.4	10.9	11.4	12.0	252	257	267
6.	MOT+T × 100+GEL	1.80	1.95	12.5	12.9	13.4	14.0	14.5	275	279	290

TABLE III

Emulsions stabilized by MIB and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emul- sion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Sod. Phosphate	Sod. Citrate	Sod. Sulphate	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre				Sod. Nitrate	Sod. Bromide	
					Thio- sulphate	Oxalate Sod.	Carbonate Sod.	Dichro- mate			Acetate Sod.
7.	MIB	.965	1.05	3.25	3.55	3.70	3.90	4.25	10.0	12.0	13.0
8.	MIB+T.60	1.40	1.55	5.70	6.20	6.4	6.95	7.40	17.5	21.0	22.5
9.	MIB+T×100	3.04	3.28	11.75	12.40	13.25	13.90	14.70	35.5	42.0	44.5
10.	MIB+GEL	23	25	110	112	114	116	118	223	235	239
11.	MIB+T.60+GEL	26	29	120	122	123	125	128	244	255	260
12.	MIB+T×100+GEL	30	33	130	132	133	136	138	267	280	283

Emulsion Type :--O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O = 10 ml. ; MIB = .05 g. ; T.60 = .05 g. ; T×100 = .05 g. ; GEL = .05 g.

TABLE IV

Emulsions stabilized by MIB and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emul- sion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Alumi- nium Chloride	Ferric Chloride	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre						Sodium Chloride	Ammo- nium Chloride
				Magne- sium Chloride	Stron- tium Chloride	Barium Chloride	Cobalt Chloride	Cupric Chloride	Potassium Chloride		
7.	MIB	.0625	.0750	.42	.45	.48	.50	.54	11	11.5	14
8.	MIB+T.60	.0995	.125	.75	.77	.80	.85	.90	19	19.5	23.5
9.	MIB+T×100	.240	.275	1.42	1.50	1.58	1.68	1.76	37.5	40	46.5
10.	MIB+GEL	1.25	1.38	6.5	7.0	7.6	8.0	8.5	227	230	243
11.	MIB+T.60+GEL	1.46	1.56	9.0	9.4	9.9	10.5	11.0	247	251	264
12.	MIB+T×100+GEL	1.75	1.83	11.4	11.8	12.3	12.8	13.5	270	274	286

Emulsion Type :--O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O. = 10 ml. ; MIB = .05 g. ; T.60 = .05 g. ; T×100 = .05 g. ; GEL = .05 g.

TABLE V

Emulsions stabilized by CPB and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emulsion Type :—O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O. = 10 ml. ; CPB = .05 g. ; T.60 = .05 g. ; T × 100 = .05 g. ; GEL .05 g.

Emulsion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Sod. Phosphate	Sod. Citrate	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre						Sod. Nitrate	Sod. Bromide
				Sod. Sulphate	Thio-sulphate	Sod. Oxalate	Sod. Carbonate	Sod. Dichro-mate	Sod. Acetate		
13.	CPB	.295	3.68	2.10	2.25	2.35	2.50	2.70	47	57	61
14.	CPB + T.60	502	.575	3.70	3.90	4.15	4.35	4.50	82	102	107
15.	CPB + T × 100	.995	1.15	7.25	7.65	8.15	8.70	9.10	171	203	216
16.	CPB + GEL	5.81	6.32	45	46	48	49	51	1105	1164	1182
17.	CPB + T.60 + GEL	6.34	6.75	52	53	54	56	58	1204	1257	1284
18.	CPB + T × 100 + GEL	6.82	7.23	60	62	63	65	68	1318	1381	1396

TABLE VI

Emulsions stabilized by CPB and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emulsion Type :—O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O. = 10 ml. ; CPB = .05 g. ; T.60 = .05 g. ; T × 100 = .05 g. ; GEL = .05 g.

Emulsion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Aluminium Chloride	Ferrie Chloride	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre						Ammonium Chloride	
				Magnesium Chloride	Strontium Chloride	Barium Chloride	Cobalt Chloride	Cupric Chloride	Potassium Chloride		
13.	CPB	4.42	4.76	15.0	16.0	17.5	18.5	20.0	31	54	66
14.	CPB + T.60	6.96	7.40	26	28	31	33	35	91	96	110
15.	CPB + T × 100	13.95	14.75	55	58	62	66	71	180	192	226
16.	CPB + GEL	76	80	362	369	375	382	390	1124	1138	1201
17.	CPB + T.60 + GEL	84	89	395	400	407	413	421	1217	1236	1300
18.	CPB + T × 100 + GEL	92	96	434	439	445	454	460	1332	1350	1412

TABLE VII
Emulsions stabilized by CTMAB and its mixtures . effect of electrolytes.

Emulsion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre									
Emulsion Type .	O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O.	Sod. Phosphate	Sod. Citrate	Sulphate	Thio-sulphate	Sod. Oxalate	Sod. Carbonate	Dichro-mate	Sod. Acetate	Sod. Nitrate	Sod. Bromide
19.	CTMAB	.359	405	2.55	2.70	2.85	3.00	3.15	60	70	73
20.	CTMAB+T.60	.532	.615	3.90	4.15	4.30	4.50	4.65	90	106	111
21.	CTMAB+T×100	1.06	1.25	7.80	8.35	8.80	9.20	9.65	181	218	225
22.	CTMAB+GEL	6.02	6.45	47	48	50	52	53	1129	1179	1200
23.	CTMAB+T.60+GEL	6.59	6.96	54	55	57	59	61	1221	1283	1298
24.	CTMAB+T×100+GEL	7.02	7.54	63	65	68	70	73	1348	1390	1411

TABLE VIII

Emulsions stabilized by CTMAB and its mixtures : effect of electrolytes.

Emulsion No.	Emulsifying Agent	Demulsification value of electrolytes in millimoles per litre									
Emulsion Type :-	O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 2 ; K.O.	Aluminium Chloride	Ferric Chloride	Magnesium Chloride	Strontium Chloride	Barium Chloride	Cobalt Chloride	Cupric Chloride	Potassium Chloride	Sodium Chloride	Ammonium Chloride
19.	CTMAB	4.84	5.20	19.0	20.5	21.0	22.5	23.5	62	66	77
20.	CTMAB+T.60	7.55	8.10	28	31	33	35	37	96	100	117
21.	CTMAB+T×100	14.85	16.35	58	61	65	70	74	193	207	238
22.	CTMAB+GEL	82	84	371	375	381	386	394	1142	1163	1217
23.	CTMAB+T.60+GEL	90	94	402	408	415	422	426	1243	1265	1319
24.	CTMAB+T×100+GEL	98	103	444	448	454	460	467	1355	1377	1430

The stabilizing power of both types of cationic surfactants and their mixtures towards electrolytes may be arranged as under :—

A study of Tables II and IV reveals that in case of emulsions stabilized by anionic surfactants and their mixtures, the demulsification value of electrolytes decreases in the following order : NH_4Cl , NaCl , KCl , CuCl_2 , CoCl_2 , BaCl_2 , SrCl_2 , MgCl_2 , FeCl_3 and AlCl_3 . Thus the demulsification power of ions opposite in sign to that of emulsifying agent that is, of cations may be arranged as under . $\text{Al}^{+++} > \text{Fe}^{+++} > \text{Mg}^{++} > \text{Sr}^{++} > \text{Ba}^{++} > \text{Co}^{+} > \text{Cu}^{+} > \text{K}^{+} > \text{Na}^{+} > \text{NH}_4^{+}$.

Similarly, for the emulsions stabilized by cationic surfactants and their mixtures (Tables V and VII), the demulsification power of anions may be written as follows '
 $\text{PO}_4^{---} > \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{---} > \text{SO}_4^{--} > \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{--} > \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{--} > \text{CO}_3^{--} > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--} > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Br}^-$.

It may be concluded that the demulsification value or the concentration of an electrolyte necessary to cause breaking of an emulsion into two separate liquid layers depends on, the nature of emulsion the method of its preparation, nature and concentration of emulsifying agent, ratio of oil and water etc., as well as on the nature and valency of the ions of the electrolyte used. In the case of emulsions stabilized by an anionic surfactant, the demulsification value depends on the valency of the cation and is largely, although not entirely, independent of the nature of anion ; in the case of emulsions stabilized by cationic surfactant, it is the valency of anion that is of primary importance. The higher the valency, the lower is the demulsification value. This is of course in accordance with the Schulze-Hardy rule¹⁴ as applicable to lyophobic colloids and suggests, as does the work of Van den Tempel³ that the presence of ions of opposite charge to that of emulsifying agent results in a decrease in the numerical value of zeta-potential, with the result that when the double layer potential is decreased below the critical value, the repulsion between approaching droplets is reduced to such an extent that those colliding with a certain velocity join together : in this way demulsification occurs.

An examination of Tables I, III, V and VII shows that there are some deviations from the strict valence rule for emulsions, for example even with an increase in the valency of ion of the same charge as that of emulsifying agent, there is a decrease in the demulsification value of electrolytes.